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PHARMACEUTICAL COLD CHAIN MANAGEMENT— REGULATORY FRAMEWORK AND PRACTICAL APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Pharmaceutical cold chain management is a complex process that involves various tasks aimed at controlling the temperature and related environmental conditions of medications and other medicinal products through the entire supply chain, from manufacturing and storage to transportation and distribution. The importance of this specific kind of delivery has increased immensely over recent decades, and with temperature-sensitive products leaving pharmaceutical companies to be shipped worldwide, distributors depend on reliable solutions for their logistics—from packaging solutions to highly advanced refrigeration devices.

AIM: The aim of this review paper is to analyze the regulatory framework of pharmaceutical cold chain management for pharmacies in Bulgaria and the European Union. An additional task in the study is to highlight some practical approaches leading to high effectiveness of this logistic process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A systematic literature review was conducted using the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines. Peer-reviewed articles published between 2010 and 2023 were sourced from databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. Inclusion criteria examining hospital pharmacists' involvement in multidisciplinary teams and their impact on patient care, specifically in hematology, were studied. The selection process followed the PRISMA framework, including title/abstract screening and full-text review.

RESULTS: Regulators such as the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) have reacted to the increased complexity that comes with the supply chain of biologics, for example, by implementing Good Distribution Practice (GDP) as a regulatory framework for distributors of medicines to ensure their viability and safety. There is no specific recommendations and regulatory framework for cold chain management in pharmacies. In Bulgaria, the legislative document in which a framework about work with this separate group of medicines can be adopted is the Rules for Good pharmacy practices established by the Bulgarian Pharmaceutical Union.

CONCLUSION: Pharmacies have significant cold chain management challenges to meet, including ensuring consistent management and monitoring of product storage temperatures across the organization, the need to meet regulatory compliance requirements across disparate settings, and the risk that temperature excursions will lead to loss of medications or a negative impact on patient care.

Keywords: *pharmacy, cold chain, management, regulation*